

Santripreneurship: How Does the Digital Era of Independence Value during the Covid-19 Pandemic at Pondok Islamic Boarding School ?

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Abstract: This article aims to discuss the process of independence values for students in the digital era by Islamic boarding schools in Poor Raya. the process is carried out to form an independent person, has soft skills and mastery of technology, but there are limitations to the use of technology that can be accessed at Islamic boarding schools, so students must be able to study independently to keep up with the developments of the industrial revolutions, especially with the Covid-19 pandemics. the demands of the students for independent study make the roles of Islamic boarding schools must balance learning techniques that are in accordance with the digital era. Another obstacle that arises is that the principle of devotion to Kyai makes the mindset of the Students to be more inclined to manage the business in the Islamic boarding school. This type of research is a qualitative research with a case study approach. data collection techniques were carried out by observation and in-depth interviews. The research subjects were students and leaders of Islamic boarding schools, and ustaz . The analysis technique is carried out with the stages of input, process and output. The results of this study are applying a santri must balance the life of the world and the hereafter. Entrepreneurship activities are carried out through training, cultivation of orchids, mushrooms, manufacturing, yogurt, printing, broadcasting, shooting services and video production. These activities can be a medium in shaping the students to become independent individuals, stimulating creative and good ideas at establishing communication with various groups.

Keywords:- Entrepreneurial Character of the Digital Era , Covid-19 , Kyai's Leadership , Pondok Boarding school

I. INTRODUCTION

Every revolution industry bring benefit and challenge to status social a country's economy. In the 4.0 era, the spirit of information democratization is so strong thus causing euphoria in human behavior using information, this is what attention in several studies on communication and the digital world. Through ease of ownership of information centers; especially conventional mass media (*mainstream*) as well as the emergence of *e-government* led to such information flows swift and no unstoppable again because all person free make and use information [1][2]. So, in this era, mastery of technology becomes a requirement and driving factors in

developing the quality of Human Resources (HR) in rapid development of information. Human resources who are considered capable of mastering technology with quickly, that is, human resources born during the industrial revolution are growing rapidly. HR that is generation Z or class man which born on year 2000 until a number of year forward which not yet could determined limit [3] [4]. related with Thing the, so generation Z as HR which will build civilization nation, ideally should master *soft skills* or abilities that are affective and psychomotor. *Soft skills* the among them *critical thinking, problem solving, communications, collaboration, and creativity or invention* . Generation Z is required to rule over allor a number of *soft skills* the so that capable prepare selfin compete in era digital [5] [6]. In era digital this, mastery *soft skills* also need offset with mastery technology which adequate, so that superior and qualified human resources will be achieved and beneficial to life socialize.

In the midst of efforts to achieve these goals, there is an obstacle that hinders all plan and destination which has made previously. Constraint the appear fromthe outbreak of a virus that hit most countries in the world, including Indonesia. At the beginning year 2020, world shocked with spreadvirus new that is *coronaviruses* type (SARS-CoV-2)and the disease is called *Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)*. Origin This virus originally came from Wuhan, China and was discovered at the end of December 2019 [7] [8] [9]. Covid-19 is currently a pandemic that has an impact on survival various aspects of human life from various generations, so humans must be fast adapt and find solutions to these conditions.

Associated with efforts to achieve human resources superior and quality, the Covid-19 pandemic has increasingly increased the demands on this generation Z in era digital this. Since pandemic occur, all activity which beginning could performed with interaction in a manner direct, moment this Required enclose protocol health in accordance with government recommendations there are even some activities to be carried out *online* or in network / online [10]. For example transaction trading switch from payment cash to using *online payments* , publicservices have shifted from processing proceduresface to face to be assisted using applications available on *smartphones* , activities The social community has shifted from going directly into the community to being carried out in person limited even

online, just as the Covid-19 pandemic has also had an impact on system education especially Cottage Boarding school. System education is wrong one field which crucial affected from exists pandemic Covid-19 besides field political and economy. Thing because the field of education concerns the progress of the nation's generation. Efforts that carried out to maintain learning and training activities for the nation's generation in period pandemic Covid-19 moment this that is activity learning start advance switch using an online system with various policies that must be considered by institution The Islamic boarding school.

Online learning activities are a form of adjustment to the education system from with the Covid-19 pandemic, so that efforts to produce generation Z are competent and have *good soft skills*, can be achieved. Competence and *soft skills* A must have for Generation Z in the digital era, that is, at least have a passion for entrepreneurship. Entrepreneur to be alternative that can be done by generation Z to be able to compete in the digital era especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. [11] stated in their research results that generation Z has a higher entrepreneurial spirit (17%) compared to generation Y (11%), so global job opportunities for generation Z will be greater. para generation Z very interested for get knowledge and Skills which relevant To use perfect destination career period front they. By because that, spirit and interest they in entrepreneurship, dig knowledge and increase Skills should more optimized. Effort optimization in increase Entrepreneurial spirit can be carried out by internalizing the values of independence towards generations Z.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Internalization of the 21st Century Generation Z Independence Value

Internalization of independence values towards generation Z can be integrated accordingly with vision learning century 21. In accordance with context education which implement vision learning century 21, UNESCO has make four pillar education, that is: 1) *Learning to how* (study for knowing), 2) *Learning to do* (learn to do), 3) *Learning to be* (learn to actualize oneself as an individual independent personality), 4) *Learning to live together* (learn to live together). Education which build competence "*partnerships 21st Century learning*" that is *framework* learning century 21 which demand participant educate have Skills knowledge, learning skills, life skills, innovation, and capabilities in field technology, media as well as information (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2018; [12][13] [14] . Conditions in which the independent internalization process of students during Covid-19, especially generation Z, is very much needed. Regarding the new policy regulated by the government that all learning that was originally based offline has now turned online. Due to the presence of the Covid-19 virus, it is dangerous and requires everyone to stay at home. The existence of this policy made the Kyai of Islamic Boarding Schools not affected by this condition, so that the students were more focused on carrying out the learning system with the additional facilities provided by the cottage. The demands of the education system with different curricula such as linking scriptures and devotion to clerics, performing Islamic rituals virtually, innovation in

entrepreneurship and managing Islamic boarding schools and in formal education life still prioritize Islamic boarding schools.

Based on statement the, in activity learning which applied in system cottage boarding school have various kinds of components. According to [17] the education system is implemented by Islamic boarding schools are as follows. First, the vision in the education system. Second, component contents. Third, structural components. Fourth, the components of the method such as the teacher as a mandate that must be obeyed and must inspire, differences in learning styles with technological linkages and the application of *Islam for Life Mystery*. Fifth, component destination get information, knowledge, skills especially for work and entrepreneurship. Sixth, assessment component [15] [16][17]. Based on the education system carried out by the cottage boarding school, there is a number of factor which becomes pedestal curriculum for process education so that walk in the same direction. The curriculum applied in Islamic boarding schools is based on the development of knowledge knowledge and technology, community needs, rights and obligations of students as Muslims with national status, management capacity of pesantren, objectives of Islamic boarding schools, government policies in the era of Covid-19 and synergy of factors which is a digital-based demand. So, process internalisation independence implemented by Islamic boarding schools through the education system and foundation curriculum will run smoothly supported by external factors by collaborating with various other Islamic boarding schools for the development of an effective, efficient and profitable Islamic boarding school- based curriculum.

B. Entrepreneurship at Islamic Boarding Schools

Internalisation values independence on basically could applied on all One of the most striking educational institutions and levels is the Islamic boarding school. Opinion society, if cottage boarding school is means development quality HR which proper held. There is development quality HR in cottage, will give contribution significant for effort enhancement period front the welfare of the people [18][19]. Based on these arguments, so cottage compulsory boarding school prepare various programs for implementation actualization and quality of human resources for the community. Cottage Islamic boarding schools also contribute to increasing the business intentions of the students through *entrepreneurship* . The manifestation of this program is called *santripreneurship*. The essence *entrepreneurship* has grown dive two period final. Though the public is of the opinion that this program cannot be realized, but the *entrepreneurship program* is a mandatory subject that is carried out in primary, secondary, advanced, higher education and Islamic boarding schools [20] [21][22]. Future prospects will increase the potential of an *entrepreneur* in Indonesia, which is still minimal, even though it has started to be associated with the SME community. Indonesia moment this requires young entrepreneurs to be able to support the country's economic growth. The number of entrepreneurs in Indonesia has only reached 0.24 percent of the total population of Indonesia of which reached 240 million, others prefer to become

employees or civil servants (PNS) [23] [44]. There is a relationship between independent internalization of the cottage boarding school participate develop potency Students for Becomes *young entrepreneur* . Potential implementation *spirit entrepreneur* for independent students, customized with curriculum cottage boarding school. Curriculum cottage boarding school arranged based on destination Islamic boarding school education namely forming the personality of students, strengthening morals and complete it science [38] [24][25].

C. *Kyai leadership*

Santri are formed with positive and negative personalities also supported by the leadership of a kyai. Kyai leadership is the most essential element of a boarding school. Already naturally that growth something cottage boarding school solely depend on the personal abilities of the kyai [26][27]. The influence of the Kyai determines the future of the santri with the mindset that he will be happy in the afterlife if he obeys and has devotion to him. With the power of the kyai, they think that Islamic boarding schools are something small without a kyai leader. Patterns like that are what automatically form a sense of trust that grows in the personality para students both about Islam and life outside and the pesantren environment [28] [29][30]. By because that, with the approval and blessing of the kyai will foster a process of interest in the *entrepreneurial spirit* . In order to realize the potential of the entrepreneurial spirit of students, the goal education cottage boarding school added with effort internalisation values independence which conducted by cottage boarding school. However, findings in the field are not in accordance with the wishes of the Islamic boarding school, namely the number of students who are pessimistic about becoming *entrepreneurs* . This is supported by the method of Islamic boarding schools with dedication that is the main thing for the smooth running of their lives in the future, by managing business in Islamic boarding schools. They hope that in this way they will be given the trust to open other branches funded by the pondok. The mindset that has been instilled if the future is to become an *entrepreneur* is expected to have support from the pondok even though the profit sharing system and the demands imposed by the government regarding students for the country. It is this process that makes the value of self-reliance of the santri based on dedication to the Islamic boarding school environment as well as apprenticeships at other boarding schools which are his colleagues. Based on problems above, then the form of *santripreneurship* as an effort cottage boarding school for print Students which quality through internalizing the values of independence, in order to be able to compete in the Covid-19 situation.

III. METHODOLOGY

Methodology study which used in study this use type study qualitative by design study in a manner simple by researcher as following.

Chart 1: Stages Design Study Simple on Internalisation Values independence in Cottage Boarding school Source : Modification from Taufik , 2013

Study this is type study qualitative studies cases based on swot analysis (Creswell, 2012; Gillham, 2000; Lodico, Spaulding, & Voegtler, 2010). Based on statement the aims, researchers want to know the internalization strategies of some independence values cottage boarding school in Poor Raya as stock Students in the Covid-19 pandemic. 2) To use connecting one case to another based on research conducted, with expectations in the form of obtaining data from entrepreneurship education at Islamic boarding schools as a basis. Study this study form effort which has conducted cottage boarding school, analyze effort internalisation values independence which implemented cottage boarding school to his students, analyze factor supporters and inhibitor effort internalisation values independence by cottage Islamic boarding schools in the Covid-19 situation.

Total informant in study this that is two twenty four informant which originated from component cottage boarding school that is ustaz/ustazah, Students and head of the hut boarding school. The techniques used when collecting data in this study were interviews, observation, documentation and ingredient audio visual. Ingredient audio visual in study that is something webinar on Islamic boarding school financial management based on information technology (IT) which support independence cottage boarding school. Study this conducted on seven Cottage boarding school in Poor Raya among them Cottage boarding school Al-Rifa'i, Al-Hikam Malang Islamic boardingschool, Kanzun Najah boarding school, Pondok An- Nur One, Two, Three Bululawang Malang Islamic boarding schools, Islamic boarding schools Bahrul Maghfiroh Poor. After conducting observations and interviews, qualitative data presentation was carried out with three stages, namely the stage of data reduction, data presentation, and delivery of conclusions. In order to provide more accurate data, data validity tests are also shown using data triangulation technique, by analyzing the data one by one as a whole, then the results customized analysis to support main literature.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation of Santrepreneurship in Covid-19 at Islamic Boarding School

This research was conducted based on the study of the phenomenon of the Covid-19 pandemic has affected various aspects of people's lives, many have been affected by the entry of this virus, especially related to continuity education in Indonesia. Though moment this world currently in condition which is not conducive, but the role of education in providing alternatives related to knowledge and experience mastery of *soft skills* and technology in developing the quality of human resources Man (HR) . Mastery *soft skills* and technology has Becomesdemands for generation Z in era digital which currently going on moment this. Form effort society in adapting and trying to find solutions to overcome the pandemic Covid-19 in thefield of education is carried out through the internalization of the values of independence integrated with use of existing technology. On generally institution education which has implemented the internalization of independent values for students, namely in the environment cottage boarding school. However, in study this found that effort internalisation values independence in the boarding school environment for students or their students not enough integrated with technology because the administrators of the boarding school area afraid that if the use of technology is too extensive it will affect their mindset towards deepening religion. However, Islamic boarding schools must also implement new policies from the government for the educational process for the future survival of their students by continuing to instill the values of developing *entrepreneurs* in order to create jobs after Covid-19 is over. That way independence will be realized and help the country's economic recovery.

Condition development quality HR for generation Z, activity learning during the Covid-19 pandemic must continue. Learning Activities this is in the form of training to improve *soft skills* and mastery of technology [31][32][33]. On period pandemic Covid-19, Meanwhile, learning activities are carried out online or in a network. Thing the because follow protocol health which instructed by government by guard so that amount victim which caught Covid-19 so that no experience increase. Though activity learning moment pandemic this conducted in a manner online, however generation Z must permanent explore their knowledge. In essence, in an effort to develop quality The human resources of the students, Islamic boarding schools have internalized the values of independence contained in *entrepreneur education* . Competition and changes that occur within multidimensional context requires the ability of students professional one to do various jobs. Knowledge, skills, attitudes acquired and developed from Islamic boarding schools with the perspective of Islamic culture and education are often considered not in accordance with the desired competency requirements. Entrepreneurship education is not only taught in the form of knowledge, but direct practice in the field of entrepreneurship in social economic aspects. It will be more useful than just information and knowledge which implanted in self Students. Education entrepreneurship which implemented in Islamic boarding schools, starting with the cultivation of

basic entrepreneurial values which naturally based religious or Islamic. There is planting values the, expected students can more easily apply and carry out the entrepreneurial process they interest.

Education entrepreneurship has applied by a number of cottage boarding school in Poor Raya. This research is supported by in-depth information on the efforts of Islamic boarding schools in internalisation values independence para Students through activity Interview. In an interview conducted by researchers to KH. Yasin as Head Cottage Boarding school Kazun Najah Stone Poor, he convey that Entrepreneurship education in Islamic boarding schools, because it can change their mindset and explore their potential talents by directly engaging in entrepreneurial practices in the Islamic boarding school area. The types of businesses managed by this cottage are the cultivation of orchids with export sales, the cultivation of roses and other plants. Among these types of businesses, cultivation plant orchid is type effort which give contribution the biggest income for Islamic boarding school business actors because they get support full from government with exists gift land as media for plant orchid.

Head Cottage Boarding school Princess Nurul Ulum Poor Mrs. Asti stated that when the process grows soul Entrepreneurship can be extracted from ability themselves, especially the support system family Becomes Entrepreneur, consistent in operate effort, ready to take risks, then this type of business will grow rapidly. The manifestation of the success of the Nurul Ulum Islamic Boarding School in Malang is the management of IO vendors for events which are the brand of this boarding school, this is also supported by the students. Don't forget the cooperative which already has 2 branches that entrust the students to take care of it.

After conducting interviews with several heads of several Islamic boarding schools, researcher also To do Interview with para Students related internalisation values independence for Islamic boarding schools and their interest in entrepreneurship but constrained the existence of the Covid-19 pandemic because they think that many entrepreneurs have gone out of business making them pessimistic about becoming true *entrepreneurs*.

The conclusion is cottage boarding school already have many programs type efforts to foster independent values through the implemented pesantren curriculum on learning activities. Since the Covid-19 pandemic, learning activities switch use system online, so that Students must could dominate use technology integrated into learning activities. The manifestation of independent values implemented by Islamic boarding schools in the current pandemic era by changing strategies which applied to Students, that is emphasize mastery technology, because there are limits to activities outside the lodge. On period the Covid-19 pandemic, mastery of technology in all fields will become a new challenge and culture for Public Indonesia, no except in field eye livelihood. As independent students, mastery of technology becomes a field for the process of buying and selling transactions. The vision of the lodge is that they are emphasized in terms of branding and promotion for stock become graduates who are independent and have integrity in

financial well-being. Students as generation Z, must capable compete in era digital though the Covid-19 pandemic occurred. Based on the research conducted, according to previous research from [15] effort internalization of the values of independence In the digital era for Islamic boarding schools in Malang Raya, it is important to form integrity that is independent, tough, has the character of Shari'a and has an Islamic culture based on faith. Therefore, efforts to internalize the values of independence in the digital era for Islamic boarding schools in Malang Raya are integrated with *santripreneurship*. *Santripreneurship* is entrepreneurship based Students (Prihatminingtyas, 2016). *Santripreneurship* one of program development small industry on cottage boarding school. This program was inaugurated by the Ministry of Industry based on sharia [34][35][36].

Santripreneurship According to NU is an entrepreneurship system by the students, is not something completely new in the world of Islamic boarding schools. What distinguishes Islamic boarding schools from other entities are the strong roots of tradition that are maintained and maintained. Scientifically and in practice, Islamic boarding schools do not want to give up their scientific and teacher training. Nahdlatul Ulama (Ulama Awakening) is the embodiment of three main embryos, namely *taswirul afkar* (revival of thought), *nahdlatul wathan* (revival of the motherland), and *nahdlatul tujjar* (revival of merchants). From the beginning, freedom of thought, national and state independence, and economic independence were the basis for the rise of the clergy. Everything has a history, including the independence of *pesantren*, special *wabil* for business independence. Kiai Haji Abdul Wahab Chasbullah's paper, namely *Syirkatul 'Inan Murabathah Nahdlatul Tujjar*, which marks the establishment of the *Syirkatul 'Inan* work association by Kiai Haji Hasyim Asy'ari at the end of the month of Rajab 1336 Hijriah is an important guideline [37][38][39].

Previously, *Syirkatul 'Inan* was engaged in agriculture. Commerce is not a priority because it is considered difficult and unfamiliar. Now it's not only the *santri* food house program to increase food security and the economic empowerment of Islamic boarding schools, the Nahdlatul Ulama Economic Institution also fosters micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs). Networks of cooperation, access to capital, and good and strong supply chains can make *pesantren* the epicenter of the people's economy. Moreover, the application of Islamic economics is now increasingly becoming an option. In addition to the four characteristics of the Prophet SAW, the attitude of *al adla* (fair), *atta'awun* (mutual assistance), and *istiqamah* (consistent) is also a principle in entrepreneurship.

Based on this statement, so cottage boarding school has get Support from government especially Ministry Industry in developing the entrepreneurial potential of students. It is supported by data from the Ministry of Religion, in 2014, Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia as many as 27,290 institutions with the number of students reaching 3.65 million people Becomes potency for growth Entrepreneur new and sector IKM in Soil Water (Ministry of Industry, 2017). Based on the statement of Dr. Agus As

Pondok Secretary Boarding school Bahrul Maghfiroh has been an investor for 3 years for his students who are interested in continuing to become entrepreneurs after graduating from the Islamic boarding school. Its businesses are processing various garments, cultivating catfish and cattle, restaurant with Islamic nuances, and processed food form yogurt, milk, and ice cream, mushrooms and coffee concoctions. Besides that, Cottage boarding school this also have management and management finance which enough good not to forget the establishment of a Halal label office by collaborating with Malang State University as a partner in managing the office. Everything is done for the sake of support independence cottage boarding school.

B. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for the value of independence of students in Covid-19

There are supporting and inhibiting factors related to the internalization of the students' independent values. It can be seen from his enthusiasm for entrepreneurship that dedication is the *input* for the purpose of this research. Meanwhile, other efforts made by Islamic boarding schools are the implementation of curriculum and education systems that are religious and have sharia characteristics. So that the formation is considered successful in making *santripreneurship*.

The inhibiting factor from the findings of this study is the limited access to time for using technology makes the process of character building into an *entrepreneurial spirit* less than optimal. Supported by the Covid-19 situation which requires everything to be online. Limited teachers related to digital marketing also make knowledge about promotion time, transactions not according to the desired target. This time limitation is still being implemented by Islamic boarding schools throughout Malang Raya so that their students are not tempted by worldly success, this is also considered a tradition because prioritizing the afterlife is real happiness and it is a mandate from the *kyai* (Dhofier, 2015; Noor, 2019 ; Suryana, Khoiruddin, and Oktapiani, 2021) . Results study this in accordance with study by Earth., et al (2018) gives results if the *kyai*'s position is the main thing to obey, because as the leader of the *pesantren*. In terms of policy, the *kyai* have different rules than adjusting the social conditions around their environment to be accepted in society. The process of character education applied by the *kyai* to his students is the independence of becoming a trader or entrepreneur, because the business he considers halal and becoming an entrepreneur is the path taken by the Prophet Muhammad SAW. Judging from the prospects, by creating many *young entrepreneurs* , the country's economy will increase, especially in the digital era in the Covid-19 situation. A *kyai* will think and be guided by the Covid-19 situation, will think of strategies regarding economic stability by using digital systems that must be emphasized regarding marketing, both independent *santri* businesses and Islamic boarding schools, without leaving an Islamic perspective, namely *entrepreneurs with morals and syar'i* (Ahmad , 2016).

Based on the results above, it can be concluded that *santripreneurship* can lead to an independent spirit of students by looking at the situation and condition of their leaders. Kyai is the person who has the most influence on self-confidence by changing the mindset of students who initially only serve until the end of life at Islamic boarding schools. The realization turned into developing a cottage business to national and international standards by competing globally or creating their own business, but did not change their identity to become a *moral* and sharia entrepreneur. These guidelines become the way of life for the students to be happy in the afterlife. Meanwhile, for students who choose their own business, the pesantren provides initial capital and will create a profit-sharing system.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings from this study are ways to cultivate the independent values of santri in the Covid-19 situation. Efforts that are realized run effectively and efficiently by utilizing digital systems for the business development process. Not only instilling religious, moral and moral values, but the use of digital systems according to sharia is also required at Islamic boarding schools. Several Islamic boarding schools throughout Malang Raya agree that the presence of these independent students will help resolve economic stability related to COVID-19. Independent students formed by Islamic boarding schools are also to adapt to the demands of the current era which requires all work to be done digitally. From an effective and efficient time perspective, due to the Covid-19 situation, people's mobility is limited. There are various kinds of businesses that exist in several Islamic boarding schools in Malang Raya, namely agriculture, animal husbandry, crafts, food and beverage processing, cooperatives and even restaurants. Meanwhile, digital-based businesses, namely video services, *broadcasting*, and printing, are supported by a business center that works with financing parties such as banks. From the point of view of managing the pondok business, the students are adapted to their fields.

Advice given by researchers, business development by collaborating or entering the MSME community fellow *santripreneurship* as a means of development in the promotion strategy. Promotion with digital marketing or holding digital marketing training. So that all products or businesses managed by Islamic boarding schools will be better known by all levels of society. With the latest innovations, trust will also grow from the public to subscribe to Islamic boarding school products. Support from family to foster an *entrepreneurial spirit* is very important in view of the Covid-19 situation where not many companies open job vacancies but are more active in surviving by creating jobs or independent businesses. For example creating *platforms* and other marketing strategy policies regarding cottage and independent businesses to all levels of society.

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